

UNDERSTANDING PANDU ROGA-A PATH TO WELLNESS THROUGH PATIENT EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In the vast landscape of Ayurvedic internal medicine (Kayachikitsa), Pandu Roga is a clinical entity that bears a striking resemblance to the modern diagnosis of Anemia. Derived from the word 'Pandu', which refers to a pale-white or yellowish-white colour (similar to the pollen of the Ketaki flower), this disease is characterized by a significant change in skin color and a depletion of the body's vital essence. The details for patient education about Pandu Roga will be the content of full paper.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is the science of life that is focused on the maintenance of positive health in healthy and eradication of ailments in diseased through its holistic approach, lifestyle practices, dietary habits, and safer medications. Malnutrition either due to inadequate dietary intake or lack of balanced diet

and population explosion in today's world has led to the development of various diseases and Pandu Roga is one of such diseases. Ayurveda described Pandu as Pitta Pradhana Vyadhi associated with Rasa and Rakta Dhatu.

Pandu Roga is characterized by the paleness of the body which may be due to reduced blood flow and oxygen or by a decreased number of red blood cells and Anaemia is one of the most common causes of paleness so Pandu Roga can be correlated with Anaemia. Anaemia is the most prevalent nutritional deficiency disorder in the world. Globally, Anaemia affects 1.62

billion people, which corresponds to 24.8% of the population. In India, Anaemia affects an estimated 50% of the population.

In Ayurveda concept of Pandu is abundantly and mentioned in various literature. The knowledge of this concept is very beneficial to treat different disorders where Pandu is a symptom and disease itself. This article presents the Ayurvedic concept of Pandu Roga (Anaemia). Hence, in this article attempt has been made to review various available Samhita, Samgrantha to find out the different descriptions about Pandu and bring all of them in a single place.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

To review the concept of Pandu Roga from different Ayurvedic literature.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Material has been collected from ancient Ayurvedic texts, Research Journals, and electronic databases.

Review of Literature

- **Vyutpatti**

The word Pandu is derived from 'Padi Nashane' Dhatu by adding 'Ku Pratyaya' to it, the meaning of which is taken in the sense of Nashana and as Pandu has been kept under the group which is classified and named based on the change in colour.

- **Nirukti of Pandu**

According to Shabdarnava Kosha 'Pandustu Peet bhagardh Ketaki Dhulisannibham' means Pandu is like the colour of pollen grains of Ketaki flower which is whitish yellow colour.

'Pandutwenuplakshito Rogah Pandu Rogah' means the disease which resembles Pandu Varna is known as Pandu.

Definition of Pandu

Sarveshu Chaiteshvih Pandubhavo Yatoadhikoatah Khalu Pandurogah. (Su.Ut. 44/4). It is called Pandu Roga because of predominance of paleness all over body.

Synonyms

According to Shushrut Kamala, Panki, Laghrak, Alas and Kumbhahwa are synonyms of Pandu.

Types of Pandu Roga

Acharya Charak described disease under five categories namely Vataj, Pittaj, Kaphaj, Sannipataj, and Mridabhakshanajanya and Acharya Shushrut has accepted only four types of Pandu excluding Mridabhakshanajanya Pandu, they are:

1. Vataj Pandu
2. Pittaj Pandu
3. Kaphaj Pandu
4. Sanipataj Pandu
5. Mridikabhakshanajanya Pandu

Acharya Harita mentioned eight types of Pandu in Harita Samhita and described Kamla, Kumbhakamla, and Halimaka as their Synonyms.

Nidana (Causative Factors)

क्षाराम्ललवणात्युष्णविरुद्धासात्म्यभोजनात् । निष्पावमाषपिण्याकतिलतैलनिषेवणात् ॥

विदग्धेऽन्ने दिवास्वप्नाव्यायामान्मैथुनात्तथा । प्रतिकर्मतुवैषम्याद्वेगानां च विधारणात् ॥

कामचिन्ताभयक्रोधशोकोपहतचेतसः । (Ch.Chi.16/7-9)

Nidana of Pandu Roga can be classified into following categories:

Aharaja Nidana: Acharya Charaka has described following etiological factors regarding Ahara:

Excessive intake of Kshara, Amla, Lavana, Ati Ushnaanna, Virruddha Bhojana & Asatmya Bhojana.

Excessive intake of Nishpava, Masha, Pinyaka, and

Excessive intake of Madya.

Excessive intake of Kashaya, Katu Rasa.

Viharaj Nidana

Excessive Diwaswapan, Vyayama and Maithun. Pratikarma Vaishmaya (faulty administration of panchakarma) and Ritu Vaishmaya (faulty management of seasonal regimen) Suppression of natural urge (Vega Dharan)

Mansika Nidana

Mansik Nidan i.e., anxiety, fear, anger, and grief have a major role in the manifestation of Pandu.

Other / Secondary / Nidanarthaka causes

In Ayurvedic literature, there is an indication of correlation between various diseases & Pandu Roga either as a symptom or as Upadrava. So, all these can be causes of Pandu i.e., Nidanarthaka Roga of Pandu. E.g., Raktatipravartana, Raktaarsha, Raktarbuda, Asrigdara or Raktapradara, Rajyakshama, Punara-Vartaka Jwara, etc. which can directly or indirectly vitiate Vata-Pitta Dosha singly or in combination & manifest as Pandu Roga.

Purvarupa (Prodromal Symptoms)

According to Acharya Charak

Tasya Lingam Bhavishyah Hridayaspandanam Rokshyam Swedabhavah Shramsathata. (Ch. Chi. 16/12) Hridayaspandanam (Palpitation), Rokshyam (dryness of skin), Swedabhavah (absence of sweating), Shramsathata (fatigue)

According to Acharya Sushruta

Twakspothnam Sthevangatrasadoo Mridbhakshanam Prekshankootsothah. Vidmutrapitatwamathaavipako Bhavishtasya Pu-rahsarani. (Su.U. 44/5) Twakspothnam (cracking of skin), Sthevan (salivation), Gatrasada (sense of lassitude in limbs), Mridbhakshanam (liking for mud intake), Prekshankootsothah (swelling over eye socket), Vid-Mutra Pitata (yellow colour of stool-urine), Avi-paka (Indigestion) these are mentioned by Sushruta.

Rupa (Symptoms)

Acharya Charak has mentioned Samanya and Vishesh Rupa of Pandu Roga in chapter 16 of Chikitsa Sthaan according to Dosha involvement which is mentioned below.

दुर्बलः सदनोऽन्नद्विट् श्रमभ्रमनिपीडितः ॥ गात्रशूलज्वरश्वासगौरवारुचिमान्जरः । मृदितैरिव गात्रैश्च पीडितोऽन्मथितैरिव ॥ शूनाक्षिकूटो हरितः शीर्णलोमा हतप्रभः । कोपनः शिशिरद्वेषी निद्रालुः

ष्टिवनोऽल्पवाक् ॥ पिण्डिकोद्वेष्टकटयूरूपादरूक्सदनानि च। भवन्त्यारोहणायसै ॥

Ch.Chi.16/13-16

Samanya Rupa

- Loss of Indriya Bala, Teja, Veerya and Loss of Bala, Varna and Agni (power of digestion).
- Karnashveda (tinnitus), Daurbalya (general weakness), Annadweshha (aversion towards food), Shrama (fatigue), Bhramanipidita (giddiness), Gatrashula (body ache), Jwara (fever), Shwasa (breathlessness), Gaurva (heaviness), Aruchi (anorexia).

Akshikutashotha (swelling over orbit), Shirnaloma (hair fall), Hataprabha (loss of body complexion/lustre)

Kopana (dislikes cold things), Nidralu (feeling of drowsiness), Alpawaka (avoid speaking), Shtheevana (spitting frequently)

Pindikodweshthana (calf muscle pain), Katiuru-Paad Ruka (pain in the lumbar, thighs and feet), Arohaneayasa (patient feels exhausted on climbing)

Vishishta Rupa: Acharya Charka had classified Pandu Roga into 5 types; based on these types Vishesh Rupas are described-

Vataj Pandu: Krishna-Panduta (black and pale-yellow discolouration), Rukshata (roughness), Aruna-Angatam (Reddishness of the body), Angmarda (body ache), Ruja (pain), Toda (Pricking type of pain), Kampa (tremor), Parshvashiro-Ruja (pain in chest-head), Varchashosh (dryness of stool), Aashyavairasya (distaste in mouth), Shopha (oedema over body parts), Aanah (constipation), Bala-Kshaya (weakness).

Pittaja Pandu: Pita-Haritabhata (complexion become either yellow or green), Jwara, Daha (burning sensation), Trishna (excessive thirst), Murcha (fainting), Pipasa, Pitamutrashakruta (yellowish discolouration of urine and stool), Sweda (profuse sweating), Sheetakamta (increase desire to take cold things), Katukasayta (feeling pungent taste in mouth), Ushnaamlanupashyata (uneasiness for hot and sour things), Vidahe Vidagadhe Anne (feeling of burning sensation during indigestion of food), Daurgandhya (foul smell of body), Daurbalya (weakness), Bhinn-Varcha (diarrhoea).

Kaphaja Pandu: Gaurava (heaviness), Tandra (Drowsiness), Chhardi, Shvetavbhasta (whitish complexion), Praseka (excessive salivation), Lomoharsha (Horripilation), Murchha (Fainting), Bhrama (giddiness), Klama (mental fatigue), Sa-da (looseness of body parts), Kasa, Shwasa (dyspnoea), Alasya (laziness), Aruchi (anorexia), Vaka-swaragraha (obstruction of speech and voice), Shukla Mutra-Akshivarchasa (whitish discolouration of urine, eye and stool), Katurukshoshna Kamta (feeling to take pungent, Hot and dry things), Shwayathu, Madhurasyata (sweetishness in mouth).

Sannipataj Pandu: Signs & symptoms of all three vitiated Doshas are present, and this is extremely intolerable because of developing complications.

Mridbhakshanajanya Pandu: Bala-Varna-Agni Nash (loss of strength, complexion, and power of digestion metabolism), Ganda-Akshikuta-Bhru-Pad-Nabhi-Mehan Shotha (oedema on cheek, eye socket, eyebrow, feet, umbilical region, genital parts), Krimi Koshta (Appearance of intestinal worm), Atisaryet Mala Sasruka Kapha (diarrhoea associated with blood and mucus).

Samprapti (Pathogenesis)

समवस्थितम् ॥ वायुना बलिना क्षिप्तं संप्राप्य धमनीर्दश । प्रपन्नं केवलं देहं त्वड्मांसान्तरमाश्रितम् ॥
प्रदूष्य कफवातासृक् त्वमांसानि करोति तत् । पाण्डुहारिद्रहरितान् वर्णान् बहुविधांस्त्वचि ॥

Ch.Chi.16/9-11

Acharya Charaka has mentioned the Samprapti of Pandu in Chikitsa Sthan. According to him, due to consumption of Nidana Pitta located in the Hridaya (Sadhaka Pitta) gets aggravated and is expelled from Hridya by powerful Vata and it enters the Dash-Dhamanya (attached to the heart) and circulates all over the body. This aggravated Pitta reaches the space between skin and muscle tissue, bringing vitiation in Kapha, Vata, Asrika, Twaka and Mamsa. This leads to abnormal types of colouration like Pandu, Haridra and Harita on the skin.

Samprapti Ghataka

Dosha – Pitta Pradhan Tridoshaja.

Pitta – Sadhaka, Ranjaka and Bhrajaka.

Kapha – Avalambaka, Kledaka.

Vyana – Vyan Vayu, Samana Vayu.

Dushya – Twaka, Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa.

Strotas – Rasavaha, Raktavaha.

Stroto Dushti – Sanga and Vimarga Gamanam.

Agni – Jatharagni.

Agni Dushti – Mandagni.

Udbhavasthaan – Amashaya.

Adhishthana – Twaka Mamsa Abhyantara.

Vyaktasthaan – Twak.

Sancharasthaan – Twak. & Mamsa

Svabhav – Chirkari.

Sadhya-Asadhyata.

Patients of persistent chronic Pandu Roga whose Dhatu gets Khara are not cured. Also develops oedema observes all the objects yellowish in colour. Sharira Dhatus becomes Ruksha and a decrease in Bala and Varna occurs and Shotha develops. Rogi suffers from constipation and passes loose stools with mucus having greenish discolouration and becomes Deena, who suffers from Murcha and Trushna.

Chikitsa

According to Acharya Charak

तत्र पाण्ड्वामयी स्निग्धस्तीक्ष्णैरुध्वानुलोमिकैः । संशोध्यो मृदुभिस्तिक्तैः कामली तु विरेचनCharak

ताभ्यां संशुद्धकोष्ठाभ्यां पथ्यान्यान्नानि दापयेत् । Ch.Chi.16/40-41

According to Acharya Charak in Sadhya Pandu Rog, Teekshna Vaman and Virechan should be done.

Upadrava

According to Acharya Sushruta Aruchi, Pipasa, Vaman, Jwara, Murdharuja, Agnisada Shopha, Kanthagata Abalatwa, Murcchha, Klama and Hrudayapidana are the Updrava of Pandu Roga.

Pathya-Apathya

Pathya Ahara

According to Acharya Charaka

Shalianna, Yava, and Godhooma mixed with Yusha prepared from Mudga, Adhaki and Masura

Jangala Mamsa Rasa.

Panchagavya Ghrit, Mahatiktaka Ghrita and Kalyanaka Ghrita used for Snehan Karma.

According to Acharya Sushruta

Pandu Rogi must use Arishta prepared from Guda, Sharkara (sugar) and Shahad (honey)

Asava prepared from Mutra and Kshara should be used.

Jangala Mamsa Rasa added with Sneha (fat) and Amalaka Swaras should be used.

Apathya Ahara

In Bhaisajya Ratnavali following Apathya Aahar are mentioned:

Rakta Sruti, Dhoompana, Vamana Vega Dharana, Swedana and Maithoona are to be avoided.

DISCUSSION

The Ayurvedic conceptualisation of Pandu Roga closely correlates with the clinical presentation of anaemia in modern medicine, particularly regarding symptoms, etiological factors, and therapeutic approaches. Ayurveda describes Pandu Roga as a systemic disorder resulting from vitiated Doshas, particularly Pitta, affecting the Rasa and Rakta Dhatus, leading to symptoms such as pallor, weakness, and fatigue. These manifestations align with the cardinal signs of anaemia, such as reduced haemoglobin levels, fatigue, and pallor.

CONCLUSION

While treatable, Pandu Roga can lead to complications if chronic, underscoring the importance of early intervention. Charaka advises aggressive therapies like Teekshna Vamana (therapeutic emesis) and Virechan (purgation) in their early stages. To effectively diagnose and treat Pandu Roga, a physician must possess comprehensive knowledge of various Samhitas, ensuring accurate treatment. The clinical presentation of Pandu can be correlated with anemia in modern medical terms, characterized by pallor due to blood deficiency, although it remains one of the most underdiagnosed conditions.

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